

INDEX NUMBER.....STUDENT SIGNATURE.....

HFNMTC, BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMS 23TH SEPTEMBER, 2021)
(PBM 4) RMP 122 NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.
OBJECTIVES

QUESTION ONE

Madam Okofo a G2P1 alive came to labour in the facility in which you work as a midwife at 8am and by 1pm she had a spontaneous vaginal delivery and sustain perineal tears

- a. What are the causes of vaginal tears during delivery - 5MARKS
- b. Mention TWO (2) uterotonic drugs you know - 2 MARKS
- c. How can perineal injuries be prevented - 5MARKS
- d. What immediate care will give the newborn after delivery - 8 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Madam Alhassan G3P2 alive came to the labour ward at 12:00am with the history of lower abdominal pain and loss of show. On examination cervical dilatation was 4cm. She had a spontaneous vaginal delivery at 7: 00am and Apgar score for the first minute was 9/10.

- a. What are the factors that influence the duration of labour? - 10MARKS
- b. In a tabular form explain the indices for Apgar score - 10MARKS

BEFORE YOU LEARN TO CARE
YOU MUST CARE TO LEARN.

Please Turn Over

QUESTION THREE

Madam Abrafi Koto a 30years old G3P2^{AA} with hospital registration number 68/18 came to the labour ward of the facility in which you work on the 23/9/2021 at 12:30pm with labour pains at 39 weeks. Following vaginal examination she was diagnosed of being in labour. At the end she had SVD at 5:30pm of live male child, birth weight 3kg, Apgar 9/10 and 10/10. 3rd stage complete at 6pm. Calculate the duration of labour at the close of partograph.

a. Using the data below, plot Madam Abrafi Koto's partograph

- 20MARKS

Time	12:30p m	1:00p m	1:30pm	2:00 pm	2:30 pm	3:00 pm	3:30 pm	4:00 pm	4:30 pm	5:00
Contractions	2:10 19secs	3:10 20secs	3:10 40secs	3:10 42secs	4:10 42secs	4:10 42secs	4:10 42secs	4:10 42secs	4:10 42secs	5:10 42
Descent	4/5							2/5		0/5
FHR	140 bpm	140 bpm	146 bpm	142 bpm	130 bpm	138 bpm	140 bpm	140 bpm	146 bpm	150 bpm
Vaginal Exams	4cm							8cm		10c
Temp., pulse, BP	36.5°c 82bpm 110/60	82bpm	82bpm	82bpm	36.7°c 84bpm	82bpm	82bpm	120/60 82bpm	82bpm	36.6 82b
Membranes	Intact							Rupt. clear liquor		Rup clea liqu

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, MAY 2013
HMDW 044: NORMAL LABOUR (RM – 9)
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
 - Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
 - Each question carries 20 marks.
 - Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.*

Question One

Madam Ofe, a 29 year old Gravida 1 Para 0, gestational age; 39 weeks was admitted on 6th March, 2013 at 2am in labour at La Palm maternity Home.

- a. Plot the information below on a partograph. - 10 marks
- b. Describe the care you will give to Madam Ofe under;
- i. Relief of pain - 3 marks
 - ii. Elimination - 3 marks
 - iii. Bladder care - 3 marks
- c. Stage two (2) advantages of the partograph - 1 mark

Question Two

Madam Ofe is fully dilated now. She is positioned, delivery trolley is set.

- a. As a midwife, how will you conduct this delivery if the position is left occipito anterior? - 10 marks
- b. Describe the IMMEDIATE CARE you will render to baby Ofe at birth. - 10 marks

Question Three

Active management of the 3rd stage is beneficial in minimizing complications of 3rd stage of labour.

- a. What is active management of 3rd stage? - 5 marks
- b. Describe how you will deliver the placenta and membranes during 3rd stage of labour? - 10 marks
- c. List five (5) observations to be made on completion of 3rd stage of labour - 5 marks

Question Four

Describe the examination you would conduct on a newly born male baby under the following headings.

- a. Head and face - 8 marks
- b. Trunk - 5 marks
- c. Upper and lower extremities - 5 marks
- d. Genitalia - 2 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM /ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION -MAY 2018
RM 14 PHYSIOLOGY OF MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

You were at the labour ward when Madam Hanson G4P3 all alive with 39weeks gestation came and complained of severe lower abdominal pain and waist.

- a. What history will you take concerning her labour? - 6 marks
- b. After the history, she was diagnosed of being in labour. Explain the hormonal theory of onset of labour - 7marks
- c. How will you recognize Madam Hanson's commencement of the 2nd stage of labour - 7marks

Question Two

Madam Alhassan G3P2 alive came to the labour ward at 12:00am with the history of lower abdominal pain and loss of show. On examination cervical dilatation was 4cm. She had a spontaneous vaginal delivery at 7: 00am and Apgar score for the first minute was 9/10.

- a. What are the factors that influence the duration of labour? - 10 marks
- b. In a tabular form explain the indices for Apgar score - 10marks

Question Three

Madam Okofa a G2P1 alive came to labour in the facility in which you work as a midwife at 8am and by 1pm she had a spontaneous vaginal delivery and sustain perineal tears

- a. What are the causes of vaginal tears during delivery - 5marks
- b. Differentiate between latent and active phase of labour in a tabular form - 3marks
- c. Mention two (2) uterotonic drugs you know - 2marks
- d. How can perineal injuries be prevented - 5marks
- e. What immediate care will give the newborn after delivery - 5 marks

Question Four

Madam Sarah Atwei a 30years old G4P3 ^{AA} with hospital registration number 68/18 came to the labour ward of the facility in which you work on the 2/6/2016 at 5:30am with labour pains at 39 weeks. Following vaginal examination she was diagnosed of being in labour.

- a. Using the data below, plot Madam Atwei's partograph - 12marks
- b. Describe how the V/E was performed after you explained the procedure and set your tray. - 8marks

NMTC – BEREKUM / ST. MARY'S CAMPUS, DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2016
(RM12)HMDW 044 PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 45MINS

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Miss Abrefi G⁴P^{3AA} a defaulter of Antenatal clinic was rushed to Suronipa health centre accompanied by her husband who is a mason. On examination cervix was fully dilated.

- a. Outline the three (3) main indications for episiotomy - 3marks
- b. How will you conduct Miss Abrefi's delivery - 13marks
- c. What care will be giving to Baby Abrefi - 4marks

Question Two

- a. State and explain any three (3) 'p's that influence progress of labour - 3marks
- b. Outline six (6) characteristics of normal labour - 6marks
- c. Describe how placenta examination is done after delivery - 11marks

Question Three

Mrs. Evelyn Obeng, 35years old gravida 2 para 1 alive, was admitted to the labour ward where you worked on 2nd May 2014. Her hospital number is 3254/14

- a. State six (6) advantages of using the partograph. - 6marks
- b. Give Eight (8) advantages of squatting position used in labour. - 8marks
- c. Enumerate six (6) factors under the physiology of the 1st stage of labour. - 6marks

Question Four

Miss Ananta-Gyata Kesiah, age 20 years with hospital registration number 491/16 having had one abortion reported to otanhunukwa maternity home with 38wks gestation on 16th May, 2016 at 1:00am. She complained of lower abdominal pain onset 12:00am (16/05/2016). Her last menstrual period was given as 31st July, 2015. On examination, SFH-36cm, presentation-cephalic, descent - 3/5th, FH-132bpm, contraction each lasting 35secs, 40secs and 45secs respectively. On vaginal examination, cervical os 6cm dilated, membranes-intact, sutures were easily felt. Vital signs checked recorded: T-36.0°C, P -70bpm, BP- 100/60mmHg. A 100mls of urine was recorded with no abnormality detected.

At 1: 30am

FH-128bpm, contractions 3: 10 lasting 40secs, p-70bpm

At 2: 00 am

FH-124bpm, contractions 3: 10 lasting 40secs, p-72bpm

At 2:30am

FH-134bpm, contractions 3: 10 lasting 45secs, p-74bpm

At 3:00am

FH-128bpm, contractions 4: 10 lasting 40secs, p-70bpm

At 3:30am

FH-140bpm, contractions 4: 10 lasting 45secs, p-70bpm

At 4:00am

FH-150bpm, contractions 4: 10 lasting 45secs, T-36.1°C, P-76, BP -110/70mmHg, no urine recorded

Vaginal examination done, cervical os 10cm dilated, descent 0/5th, artificial rupture of membrane done, liquor clear and bones just touching each other

a. Plot this information on a partograph

- 17marks

b. Mention three (3) contraindications to the use of partograph

- 3marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 15: PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL LABOUR (RMD 221)
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

You were at the labour ward when Madam Hanson G4P3 all alive with 39weeks gestation and a regular attendant of ANC came and complained of severe lower abdominal pain and waist.

- a. What history will you take concerning her labour? - 6 marks
- b. How will you recognize Madam Hanson's commencement of the 2nd stage of labour - 7marks
- c. On examination of the perineum after delivery, the midwife realized that Madam Hanson had a tear which she sutured what would be your general manage to her? - 7marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Kukubor G3P2 alive came to the labour ward at 12:00am with the history of lower abdominal pain and loss of show. On examination cervical dilatation was 4cm. She had a spontaneous vaginal delivery at 7: 00am and Apgar score for the first minute was 9/10.

- a. What are the factors that influence the duration of labour? - 10 marks
- b. What would be your immediate care as a midwife right from delivery of the head of baby Kukubor. - 10mark

QUESTION THREE

Madam Nsiah a 20year old G2P1^A came to the labour ward of the facility in which you work on the 3/7/2017 at 6:30am with labour pains at 38 weeks. Following vaginal examination she was diagnosed of being in labour and second stage ended successfully.

- a. What are the signs of placental separation - 2marks
- b. Briefly describe schultze method of placental separation - 4 marks
- c. How will you conduct examination of the placenta after delivery - 14marks

H FNMTc - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2019
PBM 11- RMP 122 – PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

You were at the labour ward when Madam Hanson G4P3 all alive with 39weeks gestation and a regular attendant of ANC came and complained of severe lower abdominal pain and waist.

- a. What sort of data will you take concerning her labour? - 6 marks
- b. Madam Handson is in the 2nd stage of labour enumerate ten(10) indications that you will consider before giving episiotomy - 10marks
- c. On examination of the perineum after delivery, the midwife realized that Madam Hanson had a tear which she sutured. How would you educate her on personal hygiene? - 4 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Nsiah a 20year old G2P1^A came to the labour ward of the facility in which you work on the 3/7/2017 at 6:30am with labour pains at 38 weeks. Following vaginal examination she was diagnosed of being in labour.

- a. How would you manage Madam Nsiah under
 - i. Hygiene - 6 marks
 - ii. Bladder Care - 6 marks
- b. What education will you give to a mother who has just had her episiotomy repaired - 8 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Okofo a G2P1alive came to labour in the facility in which you work as a midwife at 8am and by 1pm she had a spontaneous vaginal delivery and sustain perineal tears

- a. What would be your immediate care as a midwife right from delivery of the head of baby Okofo. - 10 marks
- b. How will you conduct examination of the placenta after delivery - 10marks

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Kukubor G3P2 alive came to the labour ward at 12:00am with the history of lower abdominal pain and loss of show. On examination cervical dilatation was 4cm. She had a spontaneous vaginal delivery at 7: 00am and Apgar score for the first minute was 9/10.

a. Outlin EIGHT (8) factors that influence the duration of labour?

- 8marks

Madam Alimatu Dauda 30 years old Gravida 4 Para 3^{AA} was admitted to your labour ward on 28 June 2019 at 3:00 am with history of labour pains. Her registration number is 3/ 06/2019. According to her, she has seen show. Protein and sugar were negative when urine was tested.

b. Plot the observations attached on the partograph sheet provided

- 12marks

Time	FHR	Contractions	Pulse	Liquor	Moulding And Descent	Cervical dilatation	Blood pressure	Temp And urine	Drugs
3:30 am	120	3 in 10 lasting 19 seconds	80	Intact	+ 4/5 th	4cm	100/80mmHg	36.6°c	Injection pethidine
4:00 am	120	3 in 10 lasting 40 seconds	80						
4:30 am	128	3 in 10 lasting 42 seconds	86						
5:00 am	120	3 in 10 lasting 45 seconds	88						
5:30 am	130	4 in 10 lasting 46 seconds	88					37°c 50mls	IV Rangers lactate
5:00 am	132	4 in 10 lasting 46 seconds	90						
5:30 am	120	4 in 10 lasting 46 seconds	90						
7:00 um	126	4 in 10 lasting 48 seconds	100						
7:30 im	134	5 in 10 lasting 48 seconds	100	clear	+ 2/5 th	7cm	110/70mmhg	37.5°c 200mls	Injection Amoxicla v1.2g
8:00 im	140	5 in 10 lasting 50 seconds	110						
8:30 im	142	5 in 10 lasting 50 seconds	100						

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – JUNE 2014
RM 10 HMDW 044 NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. Madam Erica Addai G3P2^{AA} arrived at maternity home on the 22/05/14 at 10:30am with labour pains. How would you admit Madam Addai under the following headings with the trolley set?
- i. Abdominal examination - 4 marks
 - ii. Vaginal examination - 3 marks
- b. Following the vaginal examination, the cervix was 5cm dilated. Use the information below and the one attached to your question paper to plot the partograph. Her LMP was 11/08/13, EDD – 18/05/15, Gestation – 38 weeks with registration number 338/13
- i. Enumerate four (4) advantages of partograph - 11 marks
 - 2 marks

Question Two

- a. Madam Yaa Serwaa G2P1^A came to your maternity in 2nd stage of labour. On abdominal palpation, lie was longitudinal, presentation was cephalic, position was right occipitoanterior, attitude was one of good flexion and denominator was the occiput
- i. When does 2nd stage start and ends? - 1 mark
 - ii. Explain four (4) physical preparation that you give to Madam Serwaa - 6 marks
 - iii. List six (6) positions that are used in delivery - 3 marks
 - iv. Describe how you will conduct the delivery with the trolley been set - 8 marks
- b. Outline four (4) immediate care you will give to Yaa Serwaa's baby - 2 marks

Question Three

- a. As part of measures used to control 3rd stage complication, Active Management of third stage Labour (AMST) has been employed.
- i. List the drug used in the Active Management of Third Stage of Labour, its dosage, side effects and route of administration - 4 marks
 - ii. Explain the physiology of third stage under separation and descent of placenta - 9 marks
- b. Describe how will examine birth canal in steps - 7 marks

Question Four

- a. State six (6) observations to be done on a woman within first to six (6) hours after delivery - 3 marks
- b. Define episiotomy - 1 mark
- c. Outline ten (10) indication for episiotomy - 5 marks
- d. List two (2) antiemetic, their dosage and one (1) side effect each - 3 marks
- e. Explain the four (4) types of perineal tears - 8 marks

RECORDED INFORMATION - MADAM ADDAI ERICA

Time	Temp	Pulse	FH	Descent	Contractions	Cervical Dilatation	Membranes	Moulding	Urine	B/P
11:00am	36.6 ^{oc}	80	144	3/5	3 in 10 minutes lasting 20 secs.	5cm	Intact	No moulding	130mls Protein - neg Acetone - neg	110 / 70 mmHg
11:30am		80	140		3 in 10 minutes lasting 35 secs.					
12:00pm		84	145		4 in 10 minutes lasting 48 secs.					
12:30pm		86	152		4 in 10 minutes lasting 50 secs.					
1:00pm		84	150		5 in 10 minutes lasting 50 secs.					
1:30pm		88	150		5 in 10 minutes lasting 55 secs.					
2:00pm		82	142		5 in 10 minutes lasting 55secs.					
2:30pm		84	140		5 in 10 minutes lasting 58 secs.					
3:00pm	36.8 ^{oc}	90	138	0/5 th	5 in 10 minutes lasting 58 secs.	10cm	Ruptured liquor clear Spontaneous ly	Bones overlap but can easily be separated	150mls Protein - neg Acetone - neg	120 / 80 mmHg

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMT-CBEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2017
RM 13 (RMD 221) PHYSIOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT OF NORMAL LABOUR
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Use the data below to plot Madam Ferkaa Eunice's partograph during labour at Kumkum Maternity Home
 Madam Ferkaa Eunice aged 39 years with hospital registration number 54411/17 was admitted at the labour ward at 6am on the 24/05/17. She is Gravida 3 Para 2 with LMP of 24/9/2016, 39 weeks gestation and EDD given as 31/05 /17. Madam Ferkaa laboured from 6am to 2pm as follows:

a. 10marks

	6am	7am	8am	9am	10am	11pm	12pm	1pm	2pm
FH	140 140	140 140	130 130	140 130	130 150	150 150	100 120	160 160	160 100
Membranes	Intact				Intact				C
Moulding	Sutures easily felt				Sutures easily felt Bones touching each other				Moulding ++
Progress of labour	Decsent 3/5 th OS 5CM				3/5 th 6cm 10am SRM Clear 6CM Decsent 3/5 th				3/5 th 7cm
contraction	3:10 less than 20 seconds	4:10 20-40 secs	5:10 20-40secs	3:10 Above 40 secs	3:10 Above 40-secs	5:10 Above 40 secs	5:10 Above 40secs	5:10 Above 40secs	5:10 Above 40secs
Temperature	37.0				37.0				38.0
Pulse	70bpm	90bpm	80bpm	90	100bpm	110bpm	110bpm	110bpm	110bpm
BP	140/80				140/90				140/80
Protein	Neg				Neg				+
Acetone	Neg				Neg				+
Volume	150mls				100mls				50mls

- b. state eight (8) advantages of using partograph - 4marks
- c. Give six (6) advantages of squatting position used in labour - 3marks
- d. Enumerate six (6) factors under physiology of the 1st stage of labour - 3marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Doris 37 weeks pregnant reported at the labour ward with lower abdominal, waist pain and presence of show

- a. List four (4) indications for vaginal examination - 4marks
- b. Mention six (6) observations that you would make on vulva during vaginal examination 6marks
- c. As a midwife how would you conduct vaginal examination - 10 marks

QUESTION THREE

Miss Abrefi G4P3AA a defaulter of Antenatal Clinic was rushed to Suronipa Health centre accompanied by her husband who is a Mason, already delivery trolley have been set. On vaginal examination, cervix was fully dilated.

- a. How would you conduct Miss Abrefi's delivery - 10 marks
- b. Outline six (6) indications for episiotomy - 3 marks
- c. Describe how placenta examination is done - 7marks

QUESTION FOUR

Miss Atunde reports to your facility with the complain of loss of liquor more than 24hours

- a. What is the effect of early rupture of membrane - 2marks
- b. State ten (5 each) delivery information on mother and baby that is documented at the closure of the partograph - 10 marks
- c. In tabulation, differentiate between Mathew Duncan and Schultze Method of placenta separation - 8marks

Perineum

Perineum